

New species blooms and emergent toxins on the Uruguayan coast

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Abstract

Climate-driven changes in coastal ocean and ecological systems are, in some cases, exacerbated by localized human activities. These ecosystem alterations can be intensified by changes in circulation and nutrient availability, which affect the distribution of marine populations, including the occurrence of harmful algal blooms (HABs). There is no doubt that the problems caused by HABs are growing worldwide. Certain HABs are expected to increase as sea surface temperature rises, expanding the seasonal bloom opportunity and species distribution range. High temporal resolution monitoring on the oceanic coastal area of Uruguay was used to understand how changes in sea surface temperature may promote the emergence of harmful blooms and new toxins. Using long-term monitoring, two toxic dinoflagellate species were detected for the first time in Uruguayan coastal waters, including *Protoceratium reticulatum*, a yessotoxin producer, and *Dinophysis tripos*, a pectenotoxin producer. The observed warming in the last decade in the southwestern Atlantic coincides with phytoplankton species composition changes. In spring 2017, a huge *P. reticulatum* bloom was found concomitant with detection of a lipophilic toxin. *Dinophysis tripos* has also shown a higher abundance since 2016, but toxins associated with this species have not yet been characterized.

Keywords: HAB, *Dinophysis*, *Protoceratium*, climate change, marine biotoxins

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Introduction

Climate change is expected to affect the frequency, magnitude, biogeography, phenology, and toxicity of harmful algal blooms (HABs) (Anderson, 2014; Wells *et al.*, 2015, 2020). Increases in water stratification due to warming and increased precipitation favor an increase in the presence of dinoflagellates and cyanobacteria (Thompson *et al.*, 2015; Gobler *et al.*, 2017). The rise in CO₂ may promote the growth of certain harmful algae (Branderburg *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, species composition is changing (Cloern and Dufford, 2005), associated with alterations in the range of species distribution (Tester *et al.*, 2020; Trainer *et al.*, 2020) at many locations worldwide, including Uruguay (Martínez *et al.*, 2017), due to climate variability. The migration of HABs to new ecosystems may create significant risk to aquatic organisms and humans who inhabit these regions (Gobler, 2020).

Dinophysis tripos is a pectenotoxin (PTX) producing species widely distributed and observed in colder regions, such as the northern Norwegian Sea and sub-Antarctic waters. This species has been found in Buenos Aires province mainly in July (Sars *et al.*, 2010) and has been associated with PTX production in Argentinean waters (Fabro *et al.*, 2015). *Protoceratium reticulatum*, a yessotoxin (YTX) producer has been detected in the region (Brazil, Uruguay, Argentina), generally in low abundances, YTX has been associated with *P. reticulatum* blooms in Argentina (Akselman *et al.*, 2015).

Material and Methods

Samples were collected as part of a weekly HAB monitoring program initiated in 1980 along the Uruguayan Atlantic coast. For the present study, seawater and shellfish samples (more than 550 samples) were collected from five fixed stations along the Uruguayan oceanic coast since 2011 (Fig. 1). The water samples were collected with a plastic bucket and a 250 mL aliquot was fixed with Lugol's solution (Thronsen, 1978) for phytoplankton analysis. Samples were analyzed using an inverted microscope (Olympus IM) following the Utermöhl method (Utermöhl, 1958). Magnifications from 100 - 1,000x were used (Andersen and Thronsen 2003) following specific keys and complimentary bibliographies (Hasle and Simps, 1986; Round *et al.*, 1990; Balech, 1988; Tomas, 1997; Gómez *et al.*, 2008; Sunesen *et al.*, 2008; Metzeltin and García-Rodríguez, 2012; Gómez, 2013; Hoppenrath *et al.*, 2013; Nanjappa *et al.*, 2013;) to count at least 100 organisms of the most frequent species (Venrick, 1978).

Biotoxins were detected by mouse bioassay with the modified Yasumoto method (Fernandez *et al.*, 2002) using the whole mollusk bodies. This method detects total toxicity but is unable to distinguish individual lipid toxins such as OA, PTX, and YTX.

The complexity, nonlinearity and nonstationarity of the climate system and HAB requires different statistical analysis to detect relationships between biological and physical forcing. The wavelets coherence analysis of the time series, permits the analysis of two signals along the time and analyses the dependence between them.

It is especially relevant to the analysis of non-stationary systems like both ecological and environmental time series and the relationships between these series, when the temporal evolution has aperiodic and transient signals (Cazelle *et al.*, 2008). This was done using the software R (biwavelet, wmtsa and itsmr packages) (<https://github.com/tgouhier/biwavelet>, <https://rdrr.io/rforge/wmtsa/>, <http://eigenmath.org/itsmr-refman.pdf>).

Fig. 1. Map of South America showing the fixed sampling stations along the coast of Uruguay (black dots).

Results and Discussion

Dinophysis tripos blooms were observed only in winter, occurring during low temperature periods, displaying higher salinity affinity and very narrow temperature range (Figs. 2 b, c). This species was observed first in 2013 (ca. week 100, August 2013) but generally in low numbers until 2018 (week 365, August 2018), when a maximum abundance was observed (Figs. 2 a, b).

Fig. 2. a) Time series of *Dinophysis tripos* abundance from July 2011 (week 0) to August 2021 (week 522); x-axis (time) is in weeks and y-axis (abundance) is in cell L^{-1} . b) Contour maps for temperature (left) and salinity (right) along the years (x-axis) and month (y-axis) with *D. tripos* abundance shown as black contour lines (maximum during week 365, August 2018). c) Range of temperature and salinity on sampling days when *D. tripos* is detected (from 2011 to 2021), shown as boxplots. The dark line in each box represents the median, with the lower and upper limits at 25 and 75%, respectively. Whiskers represent 10 and 90%, respectively.

Protoceratium reticulatum was present at slightly higher temperatures than *D. tripos* and at high salinity; during spring months, it had generally low abundance, however a huge bloom ($156,300 \text{ cell } L^{-1}$) was detected in 2017 (Fig. 3) with the co-occurrence of lipophilic toxins.

Both species show high significance with temperature, probably related to the El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) cycle,

at 2-7 years on average (Fig. 4). *Dinophysis tripos* shows a negative relationship with temperature ca. five years from the start of sampling (250 weeks; July 2016) (Fig. 4). This species was detected each year, displaying a significant annual occurrence staying from 4 weeks (1 months) to 8 weeks (2 months).

Fig. 3. a) Time series of *Protoceratium reticulatum*, abundance from July 2011 (week 0) to August 2021 (week 522); x-axis (time) is in weeks and y-axis (abundance) is in cell L^{-1} . b) Contour maps for temperature (left) and salinity (right) with *P. reticulatum* abundance shown as black contour lines (maximum during week 322, October 2017), c) Range of temperature and salinity on sampling days when *P. reticulatum* was found (from 2011 to 2021), shown as boxplots. The dark line in each box represents the median, with the lower and upper limits at 25 and 75%, respectively. Whiskers represent 10 and 90%, respectively.

Fig. 4. Wavelet coherence analysis between temperature and abundance of *Dinophysis tripos* (left) and between temperature and abundance of *Protoceratium reticulatum* (right) from July 2011 to August 2021. Colors code from dark blue (low values) to red (high values), as more red is the color higher is the coherence (which can be interpreted as correlation between abundance and temperature) at the location in the time-frequency space. A thick black line surrounds statistically significant periods of coherence.

Prorocentrum reticulatum appeared ca. four years from the start of the sampling (at 190 weeks), showing a positive relationship with temperature. Elevated abundance was detected between eight weeks (2 months) and 12 weeks (3 months) (Fig. 4).

Climate variability produces changes in the species distributions and abundance. In that vein, two toxin producer species were registered for the first time on the Uruguayan coast during the last decade; namely *P. reticulatum* (YTX producer) and *D. tripos* (PTX producer). Neither toxin can be differentiated using bioassay from okadaic acid, the most common lipophilic toxin found on the Uruguayan coast (Turner and Goya, 2015; Martínez *et al.*, 2017), thus toxins produced by each of these species has not yet been confirmed. Both species showed cycles potentially related to the ENSO influence in

the area. The emergence of harmful blooms and potentially new toxins may be promoted by changes in sea surface temperature, even for low-temperature species.

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